

Table S2 Whole-rock Sr-Nd isotopic compositions of the early Devonian granites in the Beishan Orogenic Belt.

Tectonic units	Sample name	Lithology	Age (Ma)	⁸⁷ Sr/ ⁸⁶ Sr	2sm	Rb(ppm)	Sr(ppm)	¹⁴³ Nd/ ¹⁴⁴ Nd	2sm	Sm(ppm)	Nd(ppm)	¹⁴⁷ Sm/ ¹⁴⁴ Nd	T _{DM2} (Ga)	εNd(t)	Isr	Ind	References
Mazongshan unit	BS17-1	basalt	411.2	0.70504	0.000006	0.79	564	0.51283	0.000005	1.65	6.32	0.15784	0.65	5.69	0.70502	0.51240	Zheng et al. 2019
Mazongshan unit	BS17-2	basalt	411.2	0.70555	0.000007	15.6	409	0.51280	0.000006	1.42	5.07	0.16933	0.73	4.50	0.70490	0.51234	Zheng et al. 2019
Mazongshan unit	BS17-3	basalt	411.2	0.70537	0.000007	8.08	506	0.51277	0.000005	2.06	9.39	0.13263	0.63	5.91	0.70510	0.51241	Zheng et al. 2019
Mazongshan unit	BA11-57	andeistes	415.3	0.70549	0.000012	23.4	443	0.51276	0.00001	4.75	21.1	0.13628	0.66	5.55	0.70458	0.51239	Zheng et al. 2019
Mazongshan unit	BA11-61	andeistes	420.5	0.70561	0.000013	12.4	509	0.51273	0.000011	4.34	19.1	0.13717	0.71	4.90	0.70519	0.51235	Zheng et al. 2019
Mazongshan unit	BA11-62	andeistes	415.3	0.70512	0.000011	20.6	459	0.51274	0.00001	4.35	19.2	0.13667	0.69	5.08	0.70435	0.51236	Zheng et al. 2019
Mazongshan unit	BA11-60	andeistes	420.5	0.70683	0.000007	23.2	421	0.51272	0.00001	4.29	20.5	0.12658	0.68	5.39	0.70588	0.51237	Zheng et al. 2019
Mazongshan unit	XIMZ135	muscovite granite	409.4	0.73912		197	139	0.51217		6.25	31.2	0.12113	1.40	-5.16	0.71519	0.51185	Wang et al. 2017
Mazongshan unit	XIMZ136	muscovite granite	409.4	0.73767		187	133	0.51219		5.79	29.9	0.11722	1.35	-4.53	0.71385	0.51188	Wang et al. 2017
Mazongshan unit	XIMZ143	muscovite granite	395					0.51225		5.18	28.6	0.10964	1.25	-3.28		0.51196	Wang et al. 2017
Mazongshan unit	16BS117	K-feldspar granite	404	0.73718	0.000006	170	97.2	0.51224	0.000001	12.5	75.9	0.09953	1.22	-2.71	0.70789	0.51198	This study
Mazongshan unit	16BS120	K-feldspar granite	403	0.72204	0.000006	104	133	0.51231	0.000002	12.4	66.0	0.11332	1.19	-2.19	0.70897	0.51201	This study
Huanishan unit	16BS005	K-feldspar granite	399	0.85295	0.000006	270	29.7	0.51246	0.000003	10.1	46.1	0.13184	1.04	-0.11	0.70127	0.51212	This study
Huanishan unit	16BS007	K-feldspar granite	406	0.83334	0.000007	260	35.4	0.51247	0.000006	9.30	45.3	0.12406	1.01	0.45	0.70886	0.51214	This study
Huanishan unit	16BS124	K-feldspar granite	411	0.75621	0.000005	144	47.8	0.51249	0.000003	14.8	63.9	0.14048	1.04	0.06	0.70508	0.51211	This study
Huanishan unit	16BS125	K-feldspar granite	400	0.94383	0.000006	271	18.1	0.51249	0.000001	9.84	41.9	0.14201	1.04	-0.17	0.69053	0.51211	This study
Huanishan unit	GQ01-01	GQ K-feldspar granite	422	0.83596	0.000013	400	54.8	0.51223	0.000009	5.44	20	0.16442	1.49	-6.30	0.70743	0.51177	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	GQ01-02	GQ K-feldspar granite	422	0.83940	0.000013	400	58.1	0.51225	0.00001	6.18	22.9	0.16314	1.44	-5.71	0.71813	0.51180	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	GQ01-03	GQ K-feldspar granite	422	0.83675	0.000011	394	54.3	0.51226	0.000009	4.25	15.7	0.16364	1.44	-5.66	0.70898	0.51180	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	GQ01-04	GQ K-feldspar granite	422	0.84322	0.000011	362	49.2	0.51222	0.00001	5.36	20.4	0.15883	1.47	-6.04	0.71357	0.51179	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	GQ01-05	GQ K-feldspar granite	422	0.83487	0.000011	401	56.6	0.51225	0.000009	5.59	20.3	0.16646	1.46	-5.96	0.71013	0.51179	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	GQ01-06	GQ K-feldspar granite	422	0.84472	0.000011	407	54.5	0.51226	0.000008	5.49	20.9	0.15879	1.42	-5.39	0.71312	0.51182	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	GQ01-07	GQ K-feldspar granite	422	0.80284	0.000012	372	53.5	0.51225	0.00001	5.69	21.4	0.16073	1.44	-5.67	0.68080	0.51180	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	GQ01-08	GQ K-feldspar granite	422	0.85359	0.000014	370	58.3	0.51226	0.000008	5.95	23	0.15638	1.41	-5.26	0.74166	0.51182	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	GQ01-09	GQ K-feldspar granite	422	0.85464	0.000012	358	54.5	0.51224	0.00001	5.28	20.7	0.15419	1.44	-5.58	0.73877	0.51181	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	GQ01-10	GQ K-feldspar granite	422	0.83011	0.000014	376	52.9	0.51224	0.00001	6.09	23.3	0.15800	1.44	-5.62	0.70503	0.51181	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	GQ01-11	GQ K-feldspar granite	422	0.83276	0.000007	356	59.2	0.51227	0.000008	5.28	20.4	0.15646	1.40	-4.99	0.72691	0.51184	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	YZHS02-01	YZHS monzogranite	424	0.74276	0.000014	324	71	0.51218	0.000008	10.48	46.6	0.13583	1.45	-5.70	0.66275	0.51180	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	YZHS02-02	YZHS monzogranite	424	0.81071	0.000011	300	81.8	0.51215	0.000008	8.11	36.0	0.13606	1.48	-6.16	0.74598	0.51178	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	YZHS02-03	YZHS monzogranite	424	0.79102	0.000013	303	67.7	0.51214	0.000008	9.87	43.6	0.13672	1.51	-6.57	0.71218	0.51176	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	YZHS02-04	YZHS monzogranite	424	0.79967	0.000013	335	67.2	0.51214	0.000009	9.59	42.2	0.13731	1.50	-6.45	0.71179	0.51176	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	YZHS02-05	YZHS monzogranite	424	0.80688	0.000014	303	78.4	0.51216	0.00001	6.34	27.7	0.13816	1.48	-6.26	0.73869	0.51177	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	YZHS02-06	YZHS monzogranite	424	0.81398	0.000014	312	60.1	0.51214	0.000008	10.1	44.6	0.13674	1.49	-6.40	0.72233	0.51176	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	YZHS02-07	YZHS monzogranite	424	0.80409	0.000013	334	67.8	0.51214	0.000008	11.9	52.9	0.13600	1.50	-6.53	0.71721	0.51176	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	YZHS02-08	YZHS monzogranite	424	0.80470	0.000012	321	67.1	0.51218	0.000008	9.42	40.1	0.14200	1.46	-5.94	0.72032	0.51179	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	YZHS02-09	YZHS monzogranite	424	0.79857	0.000012	341	75.1	0.51216	0.000008	9.83	43.1	0.13803	1.48	-6.19	0.71853	0.51177	Ding et al. 2015
Huanishan unit	YZHS02-10	YZHS monzogranite	424	0.79525	0.000013	299	74.5	0.51218	0.000009	9.11	38.9	0.14149	1.46	-5.87	0.72453	0.51179	Ding et al. 2015

Tectonic units	Sample name	Lithology	Age (Ma)	$^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	2sm	Rb(ppm)	Sr(ppm)	$^{143}\text{Nd}/^{144}\text{Nd}$	2sm	Sm(ppm)	Nd(ppm)	$^{147}\text{Sm}/^{144}\text{Nd}$	T_{DM2} (Ga)	$\epsilon\text{Nd}(t)$	Isr	Ind	References
Huaniushan unit	05-12-01	Porphyritic granite	402.7	0.72646	0.00001	226	209	0.51234	0.000011	3.97	18.1	0.13242	1.20	-2.43	0.70843	0.51199	Hu et al. 2007
Huaniushan unit	05-14-01	Porphyritic granite	402.7	0.72606	0.000011	173	152	0.51233	0.000012	10.6	55.8	0.11481	1.17	-1.89	0.70714	0.51202	Hu et al. 2007
Huaniushan unit	05-16-01	Porphyritic granite	402.7	0.72818	0.000013	197	155	0.51234	0.000013	7.51	38.1	0.11911	1.16	-1.76	0.70703	0.51203	Hu et al. 2007
Huaniushan unit	05-17-01	Porphyritic granite	402.7	0.72614	0.000013	192	182	0.51233	0.000011	7.10	35.3	0.12167	1.19	-2.21	0.70861	0.51201	Hu et al. 2007
Huaniushan unit	05-12-02	Mafic microgranular enclave	402.7	0.74404	0.00001	289	135	0.51241	0.000012	26.5	111	0.14404	1.15	-1.66	0.70843	0.51203	Hu et al. 2007
Huaniushan unit	05-14-02	Mafic microgranular enclave	402.7	0.75755	0.000012	346	112	0.51245	0.000012	20.6	100	0.12428	1.03	0.00	0.70618	0.51212	Hu et al. 2007
Huaniushan unit	05-16-02	Mafic microgranular enclave	402.7	0.74921	0.000012	255	136	0.51239	0.000013	19.7	82.1	0.14542	1.19	-2.20	0.71790	0.51201	Hu et al. 2007
Huaniushan unit	05-17-02	Mafic microgranular enclave	402.7	0.76807	0.000014	415	111	0.51239	0.000012	22.5	95.2	0.14292	1.18	-2.13	0.70538	0.51201	Hu et al. 2007

Ding, J.X., Han, C.M., Xiao, W.J., Wang, Z.M., Yang, X.M., 2015. Geochemistry and U-Pb geochronology of tungsten deposit of Huaniushan island arc in the Beishan Orogenic Belt, and its geodynamic background. *Acta Petrologica Sinica* 31(2), 594-616 (in Chinese with English abstract).

Hu, P., 2007. Tectonic, Magmatic evolution and gold metallogeny in South Beishan Mountain, Northwest China. Ph.D thesis, 1-155 (in Chinese with English abstract).

Wang, X.Y., Yuan, C., Zhang, Y.Y., Long, X.P., Sun, M., Wang, L.X., Soldner, J., Lin, Z.F., 2017. S-type granite from the Gongpoquan arc in the Beishan Orogenic Collage, southern Altaids: Implications for the tectonic transition. *Journal of Asian Earth Sciences* 153, 206-222.

Zheng, R.G., Li, J.Y., Xiao, W.J., 2019. Middle Paleozoic ridge subduction in Central Beishan of southern Altaids: Evidence from geochemical, Sr-Nd and zircon U-Pb-Hf-O isotopic data of Gongpoquan volcanic rocks. *Journal of the Geological Society*, <https://doi.org/10.1144/jgs2018-231>.